

GERB-HR-ED01 rlut 1hrCM v1.1

**TOA outgoing longwave radiation, monthly-mean diurnal cycle
resolving each day into 1-hour means**

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1. Intent of This Document and Point Of Contact

1a) This document is intended for users who wish to compare satellite derived observations with climate model output in the context of the CMIP/IPCC historical experiments. Users are not expected to be experts in satellite derived Earth system observational data. This document summarizes essential information needed for comparing this dataset to climate model output. References are provided at the end of this document to provide additional information.

This GERB dataset is provided as part of an activity to increase the usability of GERB satellite observational data for the modelling and model analysis communities. Whilst this is not produced as part of the standard GERB data processing, the need for a product suitable for routine model evaluation prompted its creation. Therefore, standard GERB data products have been reprocessed and reformatted, utilising additional data sources where necessary, to create a product primarily intended for comparisons with climate model output.

Users of these data should ensure they reference Harries *et al.* (2005) in any presentations or publications.

Dataset File Name (as it appears on the ESGF):

rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200701-200712.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200801-200812.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200901-200912.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201001-201012.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201101-201112.nc
rlut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201201-201212.nc

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2. Data Field Description

CF variable name, CMIP short name, units:	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux, rlut, W m ⁻²
Spatial resolution:	1° × 1°
Temporal resolution and extent:	1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means), from 200705 to 201212
Coverage:	Area bound by 60°N/S by 60°E/W

3. Data Origin

The Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget (GERB, Harries *et al.* 2005) instruments operate on board the four Meteosat Second Generation (MSG, Schmetz *et al.* 2002) series of geostationary satellites (Meteosat-8 through to 11). The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers that provide observations, approximately every 15 minutes, of the Earth's emitted longwave (~4.0 to 100 μm)

radiation and reflected shortwave (~ 0.32 to $4 \mu\text{m}$) radiation over a geographical region roughly from 60°N to 60°S in latitude and 60°W to 60°E in longitude. Also onboard each of the Meteosat satellites is the Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) which provides observations of the reflected shortwave and emitted longwave radiances in narrow bands over the same nominal region but at a higher spatial resolution. Data from the SEVIRI instruments are used widely by the operational meteorological and research community and are employed in several steps in the GERB product processing (Brindley and Russell, 2018).

The GERB emitted thermal radiances are derived from the GERB observations using information on the spectral properties of the scene derived from the SEVIRI narrow-band observations. Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) fluxes are determined from these emitted thermal radiances based on regressions utilising the SEVIRI narrow band observations. These regressions have been determined from simulations of narrowband and broadband radiance and flux for a wide variety of scene types. Spatial information from the SEVIRI instrument is also used to correct for sub-footprint non uniformity in the GERB observations.

At present, only data from the GERB instrument onboard Meteosat-9 (GERB-1) have been processed for submission to the obs4MIPs archive covering the period from May 2007 until December 2012. However, during this period, owing to operational constraints of the GERB instrument, data are unavailable for four months of each year (March, April, September, and October) and these months are not present in the record. Observing gaps in the GERB data for the other months also exist, including systematically missing data for the latter half of every February and August due to operational constraints and more randomly distributed observing outages, ranging from an hour to a few days, which occur through the rest of the record. A method has been devised and implemented to enable these data gaps to be filled, thus producing a set of monthly hourly mean products with reduced uncertainties and increasing the availability of the products for eight months of each year.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the processing chain employed to generate the 1hrCM *rlut* product from the GERB level 2 HR OLR fluxes. There are four main stages. The first ingests the Edition 1 GERB HR OLR data and generates an area weighted flux product at 1° by 1° spatial resolution for every 15-minute time interval. In the second stage these data are averaged over time to produce an hourly averaged product. Each hour interval is defined as the time-centred mean at half-past the hour, e.g. 1030 UTC, comprises the mean of data from 1000 UTC, 1015 UTC, 1030 UTC and 1045 UTC (or from those slots in this window that are available). An hourly average is produced for a 1° by 1° grid cell if there is at least one of the four observation times available for that grid cell. If no available data are available for a particular hour of a day, then the third stage is implemented, and these hours are filled using broadband fluxes derived from the narrowband SEVIRI data corrected to the GERB observations at the monthly hourly 1° scale¹. The final processing stage averages the hourly mean fluxes over the days in the month to produce a one degree monthly hourly mean product. The number of filled data points (days per monthly hourly mean) contributing to each monthly mean are used to estimate the uncertainties associated with the product. This is discussed in more detail in section 4.

¹ Broadband flux estimates derived from SEVIRI as part of the standard GERB processing are referred to as GERBlike HR data. To make these suitable for filling missing GERB data, they are scaled by the ratio of the monthly hourly 1° by 1° averages for the available GERB and matched GERBlike data. These scaled GERBlike fluxes are used to fill the missing GERB observations at the daily hourly scale before averaging over the month.

Figure 1: Summary of the processing steps employed to produce the GERB monthly hourly mean longwave flux at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ (*rlut*).

An example of the GERB monthly hourly mean outgoing longwave flux at the TOA (*rlut*) product for June 2008, plotted from 00:30 to 23:30 UTC, is shown in figure 2. The diurnal cycle in surface heating can be seen for the drier regions such as the Sahara and Arabian desert which present the highest OLR fluxes observed in the data during the middle hours of the day. The lowest OLR fluxes are associated either with tropical high cloud, or are seen at high latitudes, particularly in the winter hemisphere.

Figure 2: Example of GERB *rlut* product for hourly monthly-mean intervals for June 2008, starting at 00:30 (top left), to 23:30 (bottom right), over the nominal geographical region from 60°N to 60°S by 60°W to 60°E .

4. Validation and Uncertainty Estimate

There are three main sources of error that have been considered which are the absolute accuracy of the GERB radiance measurement, the uncertainties in determining a flux from a radiance, and the impact of missing data and filling these on the average fluxes.

4.1 Absolute accuracy

Quoted bias errors for GERB emitted thermal radiances are 0.96% during the night and 1.08% during the day for a typical full-scale radiance ($77 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1}$). The conversion from radiance to flux (section 4.2) can introduce additional bias in the OLR fluxes for some scenes of 2.6%. A detailed description of the absolute accuracy of the GERB longwave radiance measurements is discussed in Russell (2017) which considers the impact of uncertainties in the geolocation of the measured radiances and provides cautions with respect to aerosols and thin cloud contamination.

4.2 Radiance to flux uncertainties

GERB LW fluxes use radiance to flux conversions based on plane parallel simulations across a large variety of scenes. A regression analysis relates the observed SEVIRI thermal channel radiances to the associated flux, implicitly performing a scene identification. The concept behind this approach is described in Clerbaux *et al.*, 2003. The scatter about the best fit regression leads to a 2.3% (1 sigma) scene and angle dependent random error for the instantaneous products, but at the monthly hourly scale scene variability results in the residual effect being generally well below one percent. A further bias of up to 1.3% is possible due to the specified accuracy of the SEVIRI channel inter-calibration. In addition, limitations in the radiance and flux simulations lead to a high bias for hot desert scenes at low viewing zenith (the Sahara during the middle of the day) of a few percent and a low bias of up to 5% at the very edge of the GERB valid field of view.

4.3 Impact of missing data and data filling

Even for the months not affected by observing operational constraints, there are often days with missing hours. This occurs for a variety of reasons and tends to be a relatively random with regards to timing.

There are also systematically missing days data with the GERB observations in the latter half of every February and August due to operational constraints. To assess the impact of such missing data on the quality of the monthly mean diurnal product, all hours with no more than one missing day in the month were used to investigate and quantify the effect of removing days on the calculated OLR monthly hourly mean at the 1-degree scale. Days randomly distributed through the month were removed with 8 selection realisations used to assess the robustness of the results. The difference in the monthly hour mean at the 1-degree scale due to the data removed was determined both before and after filling the data removed as described in section 3.

Table 4.1 summarizes the resulting distributions of the monthly hourly 1-degree differences in terms of their mean and standard deviation. The values shown are the average over all the test cases as function of the number of days removed. In all cases no significant overall bias is introduced, but the magnitude of the expected error at the 1-degree scale increases roughly linearly with the number of missing days. For the unfilled data this results in an increase in the average standard deviation of the

distributions of 1-degree differences from 1.0 W m^{-2} for one missing day, to in excess of 4.3 W m^{-2} for twelve missing days. The comparable results for the filled data show a significant reduction in the estimated uncertainties, with a standard deviation of only 0.25 W m^{-2} for twelve missing days which have been filled. The results in the table are the average over eight different realisations of the chosen missing days and over all months and hours where there is no more than one missing day. The range in the standard deviations contributing to this average can be seen in figure 3 which shows the individual standard deviations for each individual realisation for all valid² cases as a function of the number of missing days. Results for the unfilled (top group of lines) and filled (bottom group of lines) are shown. The different colours represent the cases from different months, and the spread of each colour represents the variation in time (hour) and realisation for each month. The solid black lines show the mean standard deviation for the unfilled and filled cases values of which are shown for a selection of missing days in table 4.1.

Number of missing days	OLR flux uncertainty estimate (W m^{-2})					
	1	3	5	7	9	12
Mean unfilled difference	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	-0.02	0.00
Average unfilled standard deviation	1.00	1.76	2.33	2.89	3.51	4.34
Mean filled difference	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average filled standard deviation	0.06	0.10	0.14	0.17	0.21	0.25

Table 4.1: Summary of the difference between no missing days and up to twelve randomly removed (missing) days in the monthly hourly mean OLR 1-degree flux. Results are the average of eight realisations of days removed for all hours in the record where there are not more than one missing day in the month and are shown for both the unfilled and the filled results.

² A valid case was one where there was either none or only one missing day of GERB data at the daily hourly 1 degree resolution available to create the monthly hourly mean.

Figure 3: Standard deviation (σ) in the monthly hourly mean LW flux difference at the 1-degree scale as a function of number of randomly chosen missing days of GERB data (N). Different colours represent different months, and the spread of curves of the same colour represents the variation in time (hour) and realisation of random removal of days. Upper curves are for unfilled data and lower curves for filled cases. The solid black line represents the mean standard deviation for each set of curves.

To further increase the availability of monthly hourly mean data produced, an investigation into the uncertainties associated with the removal of consecutive days of data from the record was undertaken. Once again, as for the random removal of days, the investigation used only those hours in the record where there was no more than one missing day in the month. For these cases, from three to twenty-two consecutive days were removed prior to calculating a monthly hourly mean. Three different scenarios were considered: the removal of consecutive days from the start, middle and end of each month. The resulting differences in the monthly hourly average at the 1-degree scale due to the missing data were calculated for unfilled data and after filling with a scaled broadband product. A summary of the resulting 1-degree differences, for a selection of number of consecutive days removed, is shown in table 4.2 in terms of the mean and average standard deviation of the difference distributions. Once again, the result indicates that the removal of a significant number of days from the record does not yield a significant bias in the mean difference, but without filling there is a significant increase in the standard deviation (spatial variability) of almost 12 W m^{-2} for 22 consecutive missing days. In contrast, the comparable results for the filled data indicate a standard deviation of less than 1 W m^{-2} for the 22 consecutive days removed and filled with a scaled broadband product.

	OLR flux uncertainty estimate (W m^{-2})					
	3	5	7	12	16	22
Number of systematic missing days						
Mean unfilled difference	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.06
Average unfilled standard deviation	2.11	3.02	3.89	6.03	7.90	11.81
Mean filled difference	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	-0.03
Average filled standard deviation	0.13	0.18	0.24	0.37	0.49	0.73

Table 4.2: Summary of the difference at the 1-degree scale in the monthly mean OLR flux due to up to 22 consecutively removed (missing) days of GERB data. Results are for three realisations of the location of missing days for all hours in the record where there is not more than one missing day in the month. Average mean and standard deviation of the 1-degree differences are shown for the unfilled and filled cases.

The spread in standard deviation over the 3 different realisations of systematic removal of up to 22 consecutive days in the record, for all applicable cases, is shown in figure 4 for both the unfilled (upper group of curves) and the filled results (lower group of curves). The different colours represent the cases from different months, and the spread of each colour represents the variation over hours and realisations for each month. The solid black lines show the mean standard deviation values of which are shown for a selection of missing days in table 4.2.

Figure 4: Standard deviation (σ) of 1 degree monthly hourly mean difference in the LW flux as a function of the number of missing days (N) of GERB data in the month. Different colours represent different months, and the spread of curves of the same colour represents the variation with hour and realisation of the location of missing days. Upper curves show the unfilled results and lower curves the result after filling the removed days. The solid black line represents the mean standard deviation for each set of curves.

Figure 5 provides an overview of the amount of GERB OLR hourly observations missing in the monthly hourly mean flux products from 2007 to 2012. Areas shaded grey are where there are more than 22 days of GERB data missing, these regions occur for recurring periods each year owing to instrument operational constraints and too little GERB data is available to produce any products. Additional areas shaded grey are December 2007, May and December 2008 and August 2009 where extended satellite outages result in an unavailability of both GERB observations and the data used to fill missing observations. Where there are fewer than 22 days missing in the month and available data for filling, the figure indicates the number of days missing with zero days coloured white, one to five days missing coloured green and 6 to 22 days missing coloured yellow.

Compared to the original unfilled release (v1.0) of these products, hours in shown in white in figure 5 indicate those data which have not changed in the latest release. Those hours in green were included in the original release but the filling used in this release will improve the fidelity of the averages over the unfilled averages contained in v1.0. Hours shown in yellow are made available for the first time in this release as they were excluded from v1.0 due to the size of the errors associated with this quantity of unfilled missing data.

Therefore, this latest release of the GERB τ_{lut} product not only reduces the uncertainties associated with the data previously released, but also significantly increases the availability of data.

Figure 5: Summary of the periods when GERB-1 Edition 1 data are available to produce the *rlut 1hrCM* products from 2007 to 2012. Data are available for those periods indicated in white (no missing days per monthly hourly mean), green (up to five missing days of GERB data filled) and yellow (up to twenty-two missing days of GERB data filled). Shown in grey are those periods with more than 22 missing days of data, where the amount of data is insufficient to produce a reliable filled monthly hourly mean product.

5. Considerations for Model-Observation Comparisons

The GERB instrument is geostationary and has a fixed viewing geometry. This means that angle specific biases in the radiance to flux conversion will be location dependent. Because the longwave radiance to flux is based on a best fit regression for each view angle to simulations for a range of scenes, the error at a given view angle will also vary with scene. In addition to the fit error, errors from the modelling introduce further errors in the radiance to flux conversion. For instance, the plane parallel assumption results in fluxes exhibiting a low bias approaching 5% for the largest view angles, which corresponds to the edge of the GERB valid field of view. A 1-2% high bias is also known to exist for hot desert scenes for small viewing zenith angles (e.g. over the Sahara during the middle of the day) due to the limitations of the longwave radiance to flux conversion. (See also sections 4.2 and 4.3)

6. Instrument Overview

The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers making measurements of the TOA outgoing radiation from the Earth over the wavelength range from 0.32 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$. The instruments are mounted on the MSG satellites, these are spin-stabilised and comprise of an optical and electronic unit. The optical unit contains the imaging optics and detector system, a despin mirror, quartz filter and two onboard calibration sources (visible and thermal). The electronics unit controls the optical unit and provides data handling. The detectors are arranged in a linear array of 256-pixels oriented

north-south. The despin mirror is used to freeze the Earth view momentarily onto the detector array, adjusting the Earth's location by one pixel width for each rotation, enabling a full image to be built up over a period of approximately three minutes. The quartz filter is used to remove the infra-red component (4.0 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$) of the total incident radiation, thus providing a measure of only the shortwave (0.32 μm to 4.0 μm) component. The longwave component is derived by subtraction of the shortwave radiation component from the total radiation. The onboard calibration sources are used to monitor the performance and maintain knowledge of the instrument's calibration. A detailed description of the GERB instrument is provided in Harries *et al.* (2005).

7. References

Brindley, H.E. and J.E. Russell, 2018: Top of Atmosphere broadband radiative fluxes from geostationary satellite observations. *Comprehensive Remote Sensing*, 5, 85-113, doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-409548-9.10368-9

EUMETSAT; Harries, J.E. (2018): GERB-1: Level 2 High resolution (L2hr) top of atmosphere radiance and flux data. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, May 2020.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/bb6d82f8adbb49bf9b26a84a4c7c85>

N. Clerbaux, S. Dewitte, L. Gonzalez, C. Bertrand, B. Nicula, A. Ipe, 2003: Outgoing longwave flux estimation: improvement of angular modelling using spectral information, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, **85**, 389-395.

Harries, J.E. and 43 co-authors, 2005: The Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Project. *Bull. Amer. Soc.*, 945-960, DOI:10.1175/BAMS-86-7-945.

Russell, J.E., 2017: Quality Summary for GERB Edition 1 L2 Products. (URL:

http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1358/1/QualitySummary_GERBL2Ed1.pdf)

Schmetz, J., P. Pili, S. Tjemkes, D. Just, J. Kerkmann, S. Rota and A. Ratier, 2002: An introduction to METEOSAT Second Generation (MSG). *Bull. Amer. Soc.*, 977-992, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(2002\)083<0977:AITMSG>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(2002)083<0977:AITMSG>2.3.CO;2)

8. Dataset and Document Revision History

Rev 0 – 13 May 2020

Rev 1 – 23 Oct 2023 Updated documentation to describe the new version 1.1 product.